

Deconstruction of Lignocellulose Biomass via Ultrasonic-assisted Extraction Facilitates the Release of Soluble Sugars

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Abstract

The valorization of lignocellulosic biomass (LCB) into valuable products or energy sources stands as a promising strategy for achieving waste-to-wealth, circular economy goals, and carbon neutrality. Traditional techniques for extracting fermentable sugars from LCB are associated with high energy and time consumption, leading to increased costs. Ultrasonic-assisted extraction (UAE) offers a sustainable alternative, requiring a moderate investment of time and energy. UAE operates on the principle that subjecting a biomass suspension to high-intensity ultrasound induces acoustic cavitation, a phenomenon capable of lignin deconstruction and facilitating the release of soluble sugars. This study aims to explore the impact of UAE on fermentable sugar yield and supernatant recovery from apple pomace waste. The Box-Behnken Statistical Experimental Design model was employed for the optimization of process parameters, with particle diameter ($D_p = 90 - 181 \mu\text{m}$), time ($t = 2 - 8 \text{ min}$), and power ($P = 60 - 100\%$) as independent variables. Dependent variables were total sugar content (TSC) and supernatant recovery. The fit statistics for the TSC response model were as follows: $R^2 = 0.9481$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.8962$, and predicted $R^2 = 0.7068$. Similarly, the fit statistics for the supernatant recovery response model were $R^2 = 0.9847$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.9642$, and predicted $R^2 = 0.814$. Optimum conditions for maximum TSC ($25.91 \pm 1.22 \text{ g/L}$) with a corresponding supernatant recovery of 55% were determined as $D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$, $t = 6.5 \text{ min}$, and $P = 90\%$. Validation experiments using point prediction demonstrated good agreement between model predictions and observed responses. The findings of this study suggest UAE as a sustainable approach for obtaining fermentable sugar from organic waste.

Keywords: Lignin deconstruction, soluble sugars, sustainability, waste-to-wealth

Introduction

The crises brought about by industrialization, the increasing energy demand, the rise in greenhouse gas emissions due to fossil fuel use, and climate change have led to increased research into alternative renewable energy sources and sustainable, eco-friendly systems [1,2]. Lignocellulosic biomass (LCB) is a raw material with the potential to solve existing problems. The conversion of lignocellulosic waste into valuable products and energy through biological systems is an effective opportunity [3]. However, the resistant and complex structure of LCB is a challenge that needs to be overcome [4]. LCB contains three primary polymers: hemicellulose, cellulose, and lignin. While the content varies from species to species, it mostly consists of 35-50% cellulose, 20-35% hemicellulose, and 10-25% lignin [5].

Pre-treatment technologies are used to increase the contact of microorganisms with simple sugars and the hydrolysis of LCB in biological systems [6]. Pre-treatments are divided into four groups: 1) physical, 2) physicochemical, 3) chemical, and 4) biological. Physical pre-treatments such as grinding, milling, or converting lignocellulosic residues into chips involve mechanical breakdown, reducing the crystallinity of cellulose, and preparing for chemical or biological pre-treatments that include recovering low molecular weight components such as hemicellulose, which acts as a substrate. However, physical pre-treatments alone are not sufficient to make the biomass suitable for fermentation. Chemical pre-treatments are needed to convert cellulose into simple sugars that can be easily fermented. Oxidation, acid, alkaline pre-treatments, and solvent extraction are the most commonly used chemical pre-treatments. Research indicates that combining acid/alkaline pre-treatments with other physical or chemical pre-treatments such as grinding, steam explosion, microwave irradiation, and oxidative pre-treatment can increase hydrolysis efficiency while reducing acid/alkaline usage [7]. In biological pre-treatments,

lignin and hemicellulose can be broken down using brown and white rot fungi species or purified enzymes from these microorganisms. However, this method is less preferred due to the high cost of enzyme purification and the slow reaction rate. Each pre-treatment technology has its advantages and disadvantages. Additionally, pre-treatment is the stage with the highest initial investment and operating costs, as well as time and energy requirements in biological systems [8]. Research is being conducted to find alternative sustainable pre-treatment technologies that effectively hydrolyze biomass while minimizing existing limitations and disadvantages.

Ultrasonication is a promising green pre-treatment technology that aims to address the limitations of traditional methods, offering advantages such as reduced extraction time, lower cost, lower energy consumption, lower solvent consumption, increased extraction rates, and achieve higher yields [9,10]. In recent years, ultrasonic-assisted extraction (UAE) technology has become more attractive, with significant growth in its development through research. UAE operates on the principle that exposing a biomass suspension to high-intensity ultrasound triggers a phenomenon known as acoustic cavitation [9]. Acoustic cavitation occurs when ultrasonic waves create microscopic bubbles in the liquid medium (Figure 1). These bubbles rapidly grow and collapse, creating intense local pressure and temperature changes. This process disrupts the structure of the biomass, particularly targeting lignin, a complex polymer that holds cellulose fibers together in the plant cell wall. Breaking down lignin is critical because it acts as a barrier to accessing cellulose and hemicellulose, which are the main sources of fermentable sugars. By breaking this barrier, UAE facilitates the release of these soluble sugars and increases the efficiency of the extraction process [11]. In this study, the effect of UAE pre-treatment on the hydrolysis of LCB was investigated. Ultrasonic pre-treatment was applied to apple pomace sourced from a juice production factory, aiming for maximum sugar and supernatant recovery. Ultrasonication conditions were optimized to achieve the most effective results targeted.

Figure 1. UAE of soluble sugars

Materials and Methods

Equipment and Chemicals

The equipment used in the study includes an Ultrasonic homogenizer (Bandelin Sonopuls HD 2200 brand, Germany), UV-visible spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 Bio model), electric grinder (Demsan Terazi, Istanbul/Turkey), vibratory sieve shaker (AS 200 basic, Retsch GmbH), and oven (JEIOTECH GC 300/1000). The chemicals used are of high purity and include H_2SO_4 , $C_6H_{12}O_6$, and phenol.

Sample Collection and Preparation

The apple pomace waste used in this study was obtained from a juice production factory in Isparta/Türkiye. The pomace was dried in an incubator at 55 °C until fully desiccated and subsequently ground using an electric household grain mill grinder. The resultant product was sieved using vibratory sieve shaker to achieve specific particle sizes, with the sieving process conducted for 20 min at an amplitude of 60 vibrations to ensure a consistent and homogeneous particle size distribution (90 - 181 μm).

Ultrasonic-Assisted Extraction and Experimental Design for Response Surface Methodology Optimization

Extractions were conducted using the Box-Behnken Design (BBD) model, incorporating three factors at three levels with three central points. The independent variables and their ranges were particle

size ($D_p = 90 - 181 \mu\text{m}$), time ($t = 2 - 8 \text{ min}$), and ultrasonic power ($P = 60 - 100\%$), while the dependent variables were total sugar content (TSC) and supernatant recovery. The ultrasonic extraction process was carried out using an ultrasonic homogenizer equipped with an ultrasonic transducer. The initial substrate concentration was set at 50 g/L , and the process was performed under the conditions specified by the BBD (Table 1). The hydrolysate was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes to separate the solid and liquid phases. The volume of the aqueous phase was measured to determine supernatant recovery, and an aliquot was used for TSC analysis.

Table 1. BBD experimental points in hydrolysis with UAE

Run order	X ₁ : D_p (μm)	X ₂ : t (min)	X ₃ : P (%)
1	181	2	80
2	181	8	80
3	135.5	8	60
4	135.5	8	100
5	90	5	60
6	135.5	2	60
7	90	5	100
8	135.5	5	80
9	135.5	2	100
10	90	2	80
11	135.5	5	80
12	90	8	80
13	135.5	5	80
14	181	5	60
15	181	5	100

Determination of Total Sugar Content

The phenol-sulfuric acid method [12] was employed for total sugar analysis. Initially, 1 mL of supernatant was diluted 1000-fold, and then 1 mL of the diluted supernatant was pipetted into a glass tube. Subsequently, 1 mL of phenol solution was added, followed by 5 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 . The reaction mixture was allowed to equilibrate and cool to room temperature for 15 min , after which the absorbance was measured at approximately 490 nm against a blank solution using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. The TSC in the extracts was determined using glucose standards with seven-level calibration curves ranging from 10 to 120 mg/L . The obtained results were then multiplied by the dilution factor to obtain the concentration in g/L .

Statistical Analysis

Design-Expert v13 software was employed for the experimental design utilizing the BBD method. The analysis included evaluating the significance of the model, the non-significance of the lack of fit, the significance of linear terms, two-level interactions, and second-order model terms. Additionally, regression analysis metrics such as R^2 , adjusted R^2 , predicted R^2 , and adequate precision were examined for the two responses using analysis of variance (ANOVA). The mean and standard deviation (SD) of the validation experiment were calculated using Microsoft Excel.

Results and Discussion

Experimental Results and the Effect of Factors on Responses

Sugar Extraction

The effects of independent variables on dependent variables (TSC and supernatant recovery) in the hydrolysis of apple pomace was investigated using the UAE method with BBD. Factors affecting sugar

concentration in the hydrolysis of apple pomace using UAE were determined by ANOVA analysis and are presented in Table 2. The most significant factors affecting sugar concentration are hydrolysis time (t) and power (P). The two-level interactions were found to be statistically insignificant ($p < 0.05$). This result indicates that the factors that need to be controlled in hydrolysis are specifically the applied power and time. The fact that D_p is not statistically significant should be considered an advantage. Physical pretreatment applied to organic waste is a challenging process condition and has an economic cost. In ultrasonic hydrolysis, a D_p range of 90 - 181 μm was studied, and no effect was observed even with a D_p twice as large. Generally, D_p is a factor that affects the process in hydrolysis. As the size decreases, hydrolysis efficiency may increase. However, this effect was not observed in ultrasonication.

Based on the ANOVA analysis results, a response equation was developed for the independent variables, the coefficients of the terms in the equation were determined by regression analysis, and the sugar concentration response equation is given in Eq. 1. When the coefficients are evaluated, it is seen that the main effects of the factors t: time, P: power, and D_p positively affect the sugar concentration and provide an increase. In other words, it can be expected that the sugar concentration obtained as a result of hydrolysis will increase when the time, power, and D_p are increased. Although the effect of D_p is positive, it is relatively lower compared to the other two main factors; therefore, its effect was found to be insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

$$\text{TSC (g/L)} = -0.323 + 0.0261D_p + 4.77t + 0.0463P + 0.00168D_p*t - 0.000451D_p*P + 0.0205t*P - 0.509t^2 \quad (1)$$

Table 2. ANOVA analysis of sugar concentration in hydrolysis of apple pomace

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F-value	p-value	Significance
Model	281.47	7	40.21	18.27	0,0005	significant
X ₁ - D _p : Particle size	0.0365	1	0.0365	0.0166	0.9012	
X ₂ - t: Time	171.5	1	171.5	77.92	< 0.0001	significant
X ₃ - P: Power	24.64	1	24.64	11.19	0.0123	significant
X ₁ X ₂	0.2116	1	0.2116	0.0961	0.7655	
X ₁ X ₃	0.6724	1	0.6724	0.3055	0.5977	
X ₂ X ₃	6.05	1	6.05	2.75	0.1413	
X ₂ ²	78.36	1	78.36	35.6	0.0006	significant
Residual	15.41	7	2.2			
Lack of Fit	11.09	5	2.22	1.03	0.5603	not significant
Pure Error	4.32	2	2.16			
Cor Total	296.88	14				

Using the model coefficients, the sugar concentration at experimental points was predicted, and the differences between predicted and observed values were determined (Table 3). The residual difference is a tool used for assessing the model's fit, and it should be minimal. Validity assessments were conducted to test the validity of the model and the reliability of the coefficients. R^2 is the regression coefficient between predicted and observed values, with $R^2 (\geq 0.90)$. Adjusted R^2 indicates the suitability of the selected independent variables in the response equation. Adequate Precision is the coefficient indicating the signal value of the observed dependent variable. Predicted R^2 shows the coefficient of the independent variable predicted using the response equation.

As seen in Table 3, the regression coefficient between predicted and observed values is $R^2 = 0.9481$. The difference between Adjusted $R^2 = 0.8962$ and Predicted $R^2 = 0.7068$ being less than 0.2 indicates the fit between the model and the calculated response. Adequate Precision = 11.7864 was obtained, and being greater than ≥ 4.0 indicates that a response was obtained corresponding to the change in the value of the factors. Consequently, the response equation and coefficients can be used to predict sugar concentration under different experimental conditions. The highest experimentally observed TSC (25.31 g/L), corresponding to 50.62% sugar recovery, was obtained in standard run order 4. Using the response

equation, 3D surface response graphs were generated to evaluate the effects of variables on sugar concentration.

Table 3. Predicted and observed values, residual differences, and recovery percentage of sugar concentration obtained from apple pomace using UAE according to BBD (50 g/L initial concentration)

Run order	X ₁ : D _p (μm)	X ₂ : t (min)	X ₃ : P (%)	Predicted sugar concentration (g/L)	Observed sugar concentration (g/L)	Residual difference (P-O)	Recovery (%)
1	181	2	80	12.97	11.72	1.25	23.44
2	181	8	80	22.69	22.67	0.02	45.34
3	135.5	8	60	19.55	18.20	1.35	36.40
4	135.5	8	100	25.52	25.31	0.21	50.62
5	90	5	60	20.38	20.02	0.36	40.04
6	135.5	2	60	12.75	12.63	0.12	25.26
7	90	5	100	24.71	23.21	1.5	46.42
8*	135.5	5	80	22.48	22.85	-0.37	45.70
9	135.5	2	100	13.80	14.82	-1.02	29.64
10	90	2	80	13.57	13.91	-0.34	27.82
11*	135.5	5	80	22.48	21.11	1.37	42.22
12	90	8	80	22.37	23.94	-1.57	47.88
13*	135.5	5	80	22.48	24.03	-1.55	48.06
14	181	5	60	21.07	22.30	-1.23	44.60
15	181	5	100	23.76	23.85	-0.09	47.70
Predicted vs Observed R ²				0.9481			
Adjusted R ²				0.8962			
Predicted R ²				0.7068			
Adequate Precision				11.7864			
Std. Dev.				1.48			
Mean				20.04			

P: Predicted sugar concentration, O: Observed sugar concentration, *Center points

Figure 2. Effect of hydrolysis time and D_p on sugar concentration in hydrolysis of apple pomace (P = 95%)

Figure 3. The effect of D_p and applied power on sugar concentration during the hydrolysis of apple pomace ($t = 6$ min)

Figure 4. The effect of time and applied power on sugar concentration during the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE ($D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$)

Figure 2 shows the effect of D_p and UAE time at a fixed value of $P = 95\%$. The positive effect of ultrasonication time is particularly evident in the graph. When the time is increased from 2 to 6 min, the sugar concentration rises from approximately 10 g/L to 25 g/L, achieving an increase of about 2.5 times. Extending the hydrolysis time to 8 min does not result in a significant increase in sugar concentration. The response of sugar concentration to D_p remains constant, with no significant change observed. As noted in the ANOVA analysis, D_p is not a significant factor affecting sugar concentration. Therefore, $t = 6$ min is sufficient to achieve the maximum sugar concentration.

In Figure 3, the change in sugar concentration with D_p and power at a fixed time of $t = 6$ min is shown. The relationship between these two factors is linear, with the applied power being the most factor that increases the sugar concentration. When the power applied to the ultrasonic device is increased from 60% to 100% of its capacity, the extracted sugar concentration rises from 21 g/L to 26 g/L. Independent of changes in D_p , an increase of approximately 24% in sugar concentration is achieved solely by increasing the applied power.

In Figure 4, the effect of applied power and hydrolysis time on sugar concentration in UAE is evaluated. Since D_p does not significantly affect sugar concentration, it is kept constant at its maximum value of $D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$ to simplify physical pre-treatment processes. The interaction between P and t is significant. P and t are two most important significant factors, for example, at $t = 2$ min, an increase in power does increase sugar concentration. It is seen that the reaction time and ultrasonic power are required for hydrolysis organic wastes with complex structures. In general, increasing power may be necessary to shorten the time in such processes. However, with an increase in hydrolysis time to $t = 8$ min, P becomes interactive, and hydrolysis efficiency increases significantly due to the effect of power. Maximum sugar extraction is reached at approximately $t = 6$ min and $P = 90\%$.

Supernatant Recovery

The ANOVA analysis of factors affecting supernatant recovery in the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE is presented in Table 4. Supernatant recovery is important for deciding the feed rate in continuously operated bioprocesses for product yield. The volume of liquid phase obtained is a variable that must be known for the continuity of the process, in addition to the sugar concentration transferred to the liquid phase. Therefore, in this study, the remaining liquid volume was measured after hydrolysis, and the percentage of remaining liquid volume relative to the initial volume was calculated. The most important factors affecting supernatant recovery are t - hydrolysis time and P - power. It is observed that the two-level interactions are not statistically significant. This result shows that the factors to be controlled in hydrolysis are especially the applied power and time. The fact that D_p is not statistically significant should be considered an advantage.

The response equation for supernatant recovery was developed, and the coefficients of the terms in the equation were determined by regression analysis, presented in Eq. 2. When evaluating the coefficients, D_p positively affects supernatant recovery and increasing it. However, increases in t: time and P: power negatively affect the recovery rate. In other words, an increase in time and power causes a decrease in the volume of liquid obtained after hydrolysis. The main reason for this result is the evaporation of the liquid phase due to heat generated during ultrasonication and the formation of a paste as apple pomace particles absorb the liquid.

$$\text{Supernatant recovery (\%)} = 116.17 + 0.0231D_p - 9.08t - 0.535P - 0.0128D_p*t - 0.0104t*P + 0.000121D_p^2 + 0.792t^2 + 0.0025P^2 \quad (2)$$

Table 4. ANOVA analysis of supernatant recovery during the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F-value	p-value	Significance
Model	1317.33	8	164.67	48.12	< 0,0001	significant
X ₁ - D _p : Particle size	1.13	1	1.13	0.3288	0.5872	
X ₂ - t: Time	1001.28	1	1001.28	292.61	< 0.0001	significant
X ₃ - P: Power	112.5	1	112.5	32.88	0.0012	significant
X ₁ X ₂	12.25	1	12.25	3.58	0.1073	
X ₂ X ₃	1.56	1	1.56	0.4566	0.5244	
X ₁ ²	0.2308	1	0.2308	0.0674	0.8038	
X ₂ ²	187.44	1	187.44	54.78	0.0003	significant
X ₃ ²	3.69	1	3.69	1.08	0.339	
Residual	20.53	6	3.42			
Lack of Fit	17.41	4	4.35	2.79	0.2812	not significant
Pure Error	3.13	2	1.56			
Cor Total	1337.86	14				

Using the model coefficients, the percentages of supernatant recovery at experimental points were predicted, and the differences between predicted and observed values were determined (Table 5). The residual difference values are within acceptable ranges. Considering the precision of the materials used for measuring liquid volume, a difference of 1%-2% is acceptable. The regression coefficients used for model validation also supports this result. The regression coefficient between predicted and observed values is $R^2 = 0.9847$, the adjusted $R^2 = 0.9642$, and the predicted $R^2 = 0.814$. The difference between adjusted and predicted regression coefficients being less than 0.2 indicates the compatibility between the model and the calculated response. The adequate precision = 20.8497, which is ≥ 4.0 , shows that a response is obtained in response to changes in the value of the factors. Consequently, the response equation and coefficients can be used to predict supernatant recovery under different experimental conditions.

Table 5. Predicted, observed values, and residual differences in the percentage of supernatant recovery obtained from apple pomace with UAE according to Box-Behnken experimental design

Run order	X ₁ : D _p (μm)	X ₂ : t (min)	X ₃ : P (%)	Predicted supernatant recovery (%)	Observed supernatant recovery (%)	Residual difference (P-O)
1	181	2	80	76.19	78.25	-2.06
2	181	8	80	50.31	50.00	0.31
3	135.5	8	60	57.56	58.75	-1.19
4	135.5	8	100	48.81	50.00	-1.19
5	90	5	60	61.63	62.50	-0.87
6	135.5	2	60	78.69	77.50	1.19
7	90	5	100	54.13	55.00	-0.87
8*	135.5	5	80	56.25	55.00	1.25
9	135.5	2	100	72.44	71.25	1.19
10	90	2	80	73.44	73.75	-0.31
11*	135.5	5	80	56.25	56.25	0
12	90	8	80	54.56	52.50	2.06
13*	135.5	5	80	56.25	57.50	-1.25
14	181	5	60	60.88	60.00	0.88
15	181	5	100	53.38	52.50	0.88
Predicted vs Observed R ²				0.9847		
Adjusted R ²				0.9642		
Predicted R ²				0.814		
Adequate Precision				20.8497		
Std. Dev.				1.85		
Mean				60.72		

P: Predicted sugar concentration, O: Observed sugar concentration, *Center points

Figure 5. The effect of hydrolysis time and D_p on supernatant recovery during the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE (P = 80%)

Figure 5 shows the effect of hydrolysis time and D_p on supernatant recovery during the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE. Maximum liquid recovery is obtained at P = 80%. As can be seen from this result, the applied power should be kept at a moderate level. While D_p has no observed effect on liquid recovery, reducing the time from 8 min to 2 min increases the recovered liquid percentage from 55% to 80%. With an increase in time, liquid recovery decreases due to the rise in temperature and the increase

in the density of the liquid-solid mixture. These results are the opposite of sugar recovery conditions. In sugar recovery, an increase in time and maximum applied power increases the concentration.

In Figure 6, since D_p has no significant effect, it is kept constant at its highest value ($D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$). As can be seen from the figure, the most important effect again originates from time. At a time of $t = 2$ min, increasing power from 60% to 100% decreases the liquid recovery percentage from 80% to around 70%. In conclusion, to achieve a liquid recovery of around 80%, $P = 60\%$ and $t = 2$ min are required.

Figure 6. The effect of time and applied power on supernatant recovery during the hydrolysis of apple pomace with UAE ($D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$)

Optimization Study and Results Validation

In this study, the independent variables D_p , t , and P were utilized at three levels to investigate the hydrolysis of apple pomace using UAE and employing a BBD. These parameters were optimized using response surface methodology to investigate their effect on two responses: the release of soluble sugar and supernatant recovery. For the purpose of this study, the maximization of TSC was given utmost importance, while the independent variables D_p , t , and P , as well as the supernatant recovery, were allowed to vary within a specified range for all five samples.

The optimization conditions were generated using DOE software, selecting conditions that would maximize sugar yield with a desirability of 1.00. The results of optimization study are presented in Table 6. The optimal conditions were determined to be $D_p = 181 \mu\text{m}$, $t = 6.5$ min, and $P = 95\%$. Under these conditions, the predicted TSC was 25.17 ± 1.48 g/L ($50.34 \pm 2.96\%$ sugar recovery) and supernatant recovery was $55.00 \pm 1.85\%$. The optimal conditions generated by the software were validated by repeating two experiments, resulting in a TSC of 25.91 ± 1.22 g/L ($51.82 \pm 2.44\%$ sugar recovery) and a supernatant recovery of $49 \pm 1.50\%$. The optimization studies demonstrated that the UAE technique is an effective pretreatment method for the deconstruction of LCB. This method facilitates the release of soluble sugars and provides insights into the amount of supernatant that can be generated under specific experimental conditions, which is valuable for subsequent experiments such as fermentation.

The predicted results generated by the software were validated by conducting two repeated independent experiments at each of the predicted points (Table 6). The main reason behind validating the results via point prediction was to examine whether the developed models for the two responses (the TSC model and the supernatant recovery model) could produce observed results similar to the predicted results at any predicted point. Additionally, this validation was intended to determine whether the developed method could be reproduced at any time and place, provided that the samples and experimental conditions were the same. The results obtained in this study indicate that the results and developed models can be reproduced, thus validating our models.

Table 6. Optimization study and results validation

	X ₁ : Dp (μ m)	X ₂ : t (min)	X ₃ : P (%)	TSC (g/L)		Sugar recovery (%)	Supernatant recovery (%)	
				Predicted	Observed		Predicted	Observed
Optimization								
	181.00	6.50	90.00	25.17 \pm 1.48	25.91 \pm 1.22	51.82 \pm 2.44%	55.00 \pm 1.85	49.00 \pm 1.50
Results validation								
PP ₁	135.5	4.00	75.00	20.09 \pm 1.48	23.95 \pm 0.64	47.90 \pm 1.28	61.72 \pm 1.85	59.00 \pm 2.25
PP ₂	135.5	7.00	85.00	24.18 \pm 1.48	25.64 \pm 1.02	51.28 \pm 2.04	50.98 \pm 1.85	51.25 \pm 2.0
PP ₃	181.00	3.00	60.00	16.61 \pm 1.48	15.28 \pm 0.26	30.56 \pm 0.52	72.25 \pm 1.85	68.75 \pm 2.75

PP - Point prediction

Conclusion

In conclusion, UAE proved to be an effective method for deconstructing the hard-crystalline lignin structure of apple pomace, facilitating the release of sugars and providing useful data for future fermentation experiments. The study found that independent variables significantly impacted TSC and supernatant recovery. Model equations developed for these responses showed the effects of individual factors, two-level interactions, and quadratic factors, allowing prediction under various conditions. An optimization study aimed at maximizing TSC was conducted using DOE software, and the results were validated through repeated experiments at predicted optimal conditions. Further validation at different points confirmed the consistency of the experimental and predicted results, enhancing the reproducibility of the models.

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